

EFFECT OF MINIMUM TILLAGE UNPUDDLED TRANSPLANTING ON YIELD PERFORMANCE OF FOUR AMAN RICE VARIETIES

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An on-farm experiment was conducted at the farmer's field located at the Gauriopur upazilla under Mymensingh district of Bangladesh during July–November 2013. Performance of four aman rice varieties (BR 11, BRRI dhan46, BRRI dhan52 and BINA Dhan-7) was evaluated under minimum tillage unpuddled transplanting (MTUT) system where conventional tillage (CT) was the control. The result revealed that the varieties exerted significant effect on most of the parameters except the number of hills m^{-2} , panicle length, fertile grains panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight and harvest index. BR11 yielded the highest grain, straw and biological yields and BCR which might be attributed from the highest number of total tillers and effective tillers m^{-2} . BRRI dhan52 yielded the lowest followed by BINA Dhan-7 and BRRI dhan46. Except the number of non-effective tillers m^{-2} and BCR, the effect of tillage methods was not significant in case of all the parameters. The lower number of non-effective tillers m^{-2} and the higher BCR was recorded from MTUT. The treatment interaction was not significant for all the plant parameters except the number of total, effective and non-effective tillers m^{-2} . The highest total tillers and effective tillers m^{-2} and BCR were recorded from BR11 under MTUT while the highest number of non-effective tillers m^{-2} was recorded from BINA Dhan-7 under CT. Hence, it can be concluded that farmers could be benefited more through cultivating BR11 under MTUT.